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THE OBJECTIVE NEED FOR THE ORGANIZATION OF TOURISM SERVICES AND ITS SOCIO-ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the objective need for the organization of tourism services and its socio-economic significance and consequences.

Tourism activity in Uzbekistan has been considered at the level of state policy since the early days of independence. All the necessary organizational and legal mechanisms for the development of tourism have been created, important normative documents have been adopted, and this work is still ongoing. In order to develop tourism in our country, to raise it to new heights, to make our country one of the world's tourism centers, it is necessary, first of all, to create a basis for the formation of a market of tourism services. It should be noted that the tourism industry plays an important role in the development of the economies of countries and regions, and it is one of the priorities of the twenty-first century world economy.

In the modern western economy, tourism is seen as a complex socio-economic system,

in which the tourist tourism industry is seen as a whole of society, tourism policy and economy. At the same time, economic problems are analyzed together with social and ecological aspects of tourism. The point is that today life strategies and lifestyles are formed within the same socio-political foundations as a rule, they occur with a certain status of the individual in the social system. But if the lifestyle of members of another social group becomes important to the individual, then he is ready to show that he belongs to that group by expressing himself in a way of life that conforms to moral consumption patterns. The segment of political and cultural knowledge tourism requirements is expanding. A large influx of travelers seeking to explore the culture and art traditions of other peoples and countries is moving to Europe, Asia and the Middle

East. There is a tradition of expanding the political and cultural motivations of tourists for sports, health and other types of tourism. Political and cultural studies In the development of tourism, the efforts of the government and local administration to carefully preserve the cultural monuments and manage the flow of tourists to them play an important role.

A. Maslow points out that self-activating habits are inherent in many of the problems of the average person: guilt, anxiety, grief, internal conflicts, and so on. But their main difference is their commitment to the chosen job and their values. This makes them stony in the fight for their cause. At first glance, this category is less promising for inclusion in tourism activities due to its focus on aspects related to the other person type and the insignificance of social attention to life. However, an appropriately structured strategy for this category of work can turn it into a clear segment of the demand market. The symbol and image of famous historical figures in the field of religion, art, politics can travel to places that are important to him. A journey in which a person creates additional conditions for the realization of the spiritual sphere: in this he fully expresses himself in his professional direction. Marketing research should not only reveal the typical social, political and cultural lifestyles of a certain age, but also determine the relationship between lifestyles and consumer motives and behavior.

The tourism sector is designed to meet the needs of tourists themselves and organizations that are directly or indirectly involved in the organization of their products. It includes the following types of services.

1. On accommodation of tourists (hotels, motels, campsites, boarding houses, sanatoriums, tourist bases, etc.).
2. To provide catering to tourists (restaurants, cafes, bars, etc.)
3. Transportation of tourists across the country in different types of passenger transport and transit through other parts of the country.
4. Excursion services (interpreters, groups of guides).
5. Services to satisfy cultural interests (visits to theaters, cinemas, concert halls, parks, nature and historical reserves, sports competitions and other events).
6. To meet the practical and scientific interests of tourists (participation in congresses, assemblies, scientific conferences, seminars, fairs and exhibitions, participation in general and special purpose trade events).
7. General and special purpose trade services of trade enterprises (sale of gifts, postcards, etc.)
8. Insurance and medical services.
9. Advertising and service (sales) services (development of travel routes, transportation, accommodation).
10. Services of administrative control bodies (rent, quarantine, currency, customs, police services, as well as services for registration of documents, visas, passports).
11. Information services (newspapers, magazines, travelogues about tourism resources in a particular region of the globe, customs and border clearance means and the exchange rate in the

country of issue, types of transport, their directions and prices).

12. Nature and cultural protection services of environmental services (inspections on protection of historical and cultural monuments).

Speaking about the development of tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan, it is important to focus on the division of the country into major tourist regions. Today, there are four main tourist regions in the country: Fergana, Samarkand-Bukhara, Tashkent and Khorezm. The Fergana tourism region includes the Fergana Valley. Its tourist resources include archeological excavations and architectural monuments, favorable natural conditions, products of traditional folk crafts and art, industrial and agricultural complexes. The presence of a wide network of roads and railways here also allows the Fergana region to be used for tourism purposes, to locate tourist bases and recreation areas throughout its territory. Tashkent tourism region has universal potential for the further development of all types of tourism. Cultural monuments in this tourist area, modern life of the capital region, buildings, new towns and villages, modern culture, nature of the region, rich landscape, colorful flora and fauna are important factors that make it attractive. The road and rail network connects the tourist centers of the Tashkent tourism region and allows the development of railway and road tourism around the city. The Samarkand-Bukhara tourism region includes Samarkand, Bukhara and Navoi regions. The world-famous architectural monuments of Samarkand and Bukhara are the basis for the development of tourism in the region. In

addition, the railway and a wide network of highways passing through the Zarafshan River, the low passes and good trails passing through the Zarafshan mountain range are very favorable factors for the development of tourism in the region. The potential of the Khorezm tourist region is mainly based on the Ichan-Kala Nature Reserve in Khiva, which is rich in historical and architectural monuments. Along with the existing tourism regions, there are other promising regions: Jizzakh, Karshi-Termez and Middle Karakalpakstan. In the future, the development of existing opportunities in these regions may lead to further expansion of the market of tourism services in our country.

Current trends in the development of tourism show that its impact on both the world economy and the economies of individual countries and regions is growing. Tourism is becoming a major independent sector of the national economy, working to meet the specific needs of the population. Due to the diversity of these needs, tourism is one of the factors that have a multiplier effect on the development of the national economy, involving not only tourism enterprises but also enterprises in other sectors. In addition, tourism is one of the basic needs of people, which significantly helps people to reduce the emotional and psychological negative effects of the rapid development of science and technology, labor intensity.

In contrast to many other countries, the tourism industry in Uzbekistan is underdeveloped. The study requires the expansion of the tourism education system, the development of programs that ensure the development of specific regions.

Tourism contributes to the overall economic growth and development of less developed regions. Opening tourist centers in underdeveloped areas is the main method of many countries. The establishment of tourist centers in mountainous and rural areas depends on the living conditions of the population for the development of these areas. To determine the future of tourism development, first of all, it is necessary to study in depth the material and technical base, the scale of tourist resources and the demand for this tourist product. In this case, the cost of tourist resources should not be overestimated. For example, a historical monument in a particular region may be of interest only to the place itself, while in the international arena many other monuments may not be so important and may not attract tourists, and therefore in such areas material it is impossible to get much benefit from the creation of a technical base. Thus, the tourist center built in the district will lead to its development.

At present, the model of the impact of tourism on sectors of the economy is much more complex and is based on statistical materials rather than theoretical hypotheses and principles. But so far in the tourism economy, the P. Rotrow model is recognized by influential people as a classic model. Despite the fact that the world economy and tourism have completely changed (compared to 1952), the Rothrow hypothesis is not only outdated, but continues to be substantiated by new trends and statistics.

At present, in order to ensure the overall development of the tourism industry and the creation of a competitive tourism product, the necessary reforms in the sector

are being consistently implemented. Reforms in the field of tourism in Uzbekistan can be divided into four stages. Formation of a new management system in the network, the creation of additional types of business to help run the tourism business, the organization of banking, auditing, consulting services, the establishment of regional branches of tourism in the regions, international tourism promotion, licensing of privatized tourism enterprises. special attention was paid to the issues. The first normative document developed in the field of tourism is the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 27, 1992 "On the establishment of Uzbektourism" and the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 20, 1992. - Resolution of October "On the organization of the activities of the National Company" Uzbektourism ". The main purpose of this decree and resolution is to build a world-class tourism system in our country, improve the management of this sector, increase its economic efficiency, as well as the transfer of existing and former tourist organizations and institutions of the former Soviet Union. taken. This decree served as a program for improving the tourism sector in Uzbekistan, raising it to a new level, the creation of the National Company "Uzbektourism".

In 1993, the National Company "Uzbektourism" became a full member of the World Tourism Organization (WTO), which, in turn, served as an important factor in the development of international tourism.

In 1994, at the initiative of UNESCO and the Government of Uzbekistan, Samarkand

adopted the Samarkand Declaration on the development of international tourism in the cities of the Great Silk Road. During this period, the "Program for Privatization and Denationalization of Tourism Enterprises", developed in 1994, played an important role in the implementation of deep, systemic and institutional changes.

During 1994-1995, 87.8% of tourist facilities of the National Company "Uzbektourism" were privatized and denationalized.

The main centers of international tourism are located in developed economies, and tourism has become a symbol of the prosperity of the "middle class" and the mass consumption of products. In developing countries, as P. Rotou noted, the domestic tourism service sector is developing rapidly as a means of income multiplication, local employment and infrastructure development is accelerating. Foreign tourism is developing with investment. The World Tourism Organization characterized the dynamics of the global tourism market from the early 1990s to the 2000s as follows;

- The growth rate of services was 3.7% per year.
 - Growth was mainly achieved in the markets of the Middle East, Central and South America and Europe in Asia;
 - The most favorable conditions for receiving tourists have emerged in Asia. All other regions have moderate growth prospects.
 - Domestic (national) tourism has developed at a high rate.
 - Long-term international tourism has grown at a higher rate than in the past.
 - The influence of external factors on tourism is increasing (economic situation, political situation, level of travel safety);
 - Tourism:
 - computer reservation system;
 - technological development;
 - electronic information;
- communication systems had a significant impact.
- The role of marketing research in regulating tourism policy has grown.
- At present, the reforms being implemented by the state in the development of tourism infrastructure are yielding positive results.

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